

DEVELOPMENT OF MULTIPURPOSE AGRI VEHICLE TO REDUCE THE FARMERS EFFORT

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ABSTRACT

Farming is the backbone of Indian economy. In India, two types of agricultural methods are used, manual method and mechanize type method. Mechanization involves the use of a hybrid device between the power source and the work. Mechanization in agriculture made farming easier and quick. The agriculture machineries that are used now days are costlier and cannot be afforded by most of farmer with rural background. Most of the farmers in India own's very small pieces of land and owning these costlier machines may not be feasible for them. Most farmers are still stick to their old ways. The fact that most of the farmer are low level income earners, they cannot invest on the purchase of large machine. The proposed idea implements the vehicle to perform the functions such as ploughing, weed removing, seed sowing, spraying and levelling operation. The machine will cultivate and sow the farm by considering particular rows and specific column at fixed distance depending on crop. Moreover, the vehicle can be controlled manually by driving the vehicle using seating arrangement. This agricultural vehicle will be running with batteries and charged by using Solar panel.

KEYWORDS: Agriculture vehicle, Battery powered, Multipurpose, Ploughing, Sowing, Spraying, Weeding removal.

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture has been the backbone of the Indian economy and it will continue to remain so for a long time. India ranks second worldwide in farm outputs. As per 2023, agriculture employed more than 50% of the Indian workforce and contributed approximately 15% to the country's GDP.[6]. Agriculture considers many factors like weather, type of crops, type of lands, land area etc. Due to socio-economic reasons amount of land per family or head is becoming less and less. This has led to increased number of small and medium scale farmers.[1]

It is very essential to discover and implement new idea in this field, though lot of work has been done in this area. Talking about past in 1951, there were just 8635 tractors being used and every one of them were imported. Creation of tractors initiated during 1961-62, turning out 880 of them. This figure has crested to more than 262,000 out of 1999-2000. The offer of tractors in 2003-2004 was 172,000. Now, India is the biggest maker of tractors on the planet. Farmers nowadays pay plenty of cash on machines that facilitate them to decrease labor work and increase yield of crops. Due to the fact that agriculture plays an important role in the development of the economy of our country, some problems are still associated with the production of agriculture.[1]. Most of the agricultural operations in larger parts are carried on by human hand using simple and conventional tools and implements like wooden plough, sickle etc. Little or no use of machines is made in ploughing, sowing, irrigating, weeding, harvesting threshing and transporting the crops. This is specially the case with small and marginal farmers. It results in huge wastage of human labor and in low yields per capita labor force.[6]

So, we are introducing this multipurpose agriculture machine. Generally, cultivation of any crop involves various steps like ploughing, harvesting, sowing, and irrigation. Farmer has to use various agricultural equipment's and labors for caring out these steps, our purpose is to combine all the individual tools to provide farmers with multipurpose equipment which implements all the scientific farming techniques and specifications, suitable for all type of seed-to-seed cultivation with minimum cost as possible. All this can be done in this same machine.

This multipurpose Argi vehicle is equipment which is used for agricultural processes like ploughing, sowing seeds, weed removal and fertilizer.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Gaikwad S.N, Akash Shrikant, Omkar SopanHirve, Akshay Bhairavanath vyavarahare, KunalBaluBhise. [2022],"Multipurpose Agriculture Equipment for Seeding, Spraying and Mulching" In this research paper author has mentioned about the seeding, spraying and mulching, focus on designing a machine that is affordable for everyone, reduces labour cost, and minimizes operational time. It aims to address key issues such as lack of mechanization, excessive manual effort, and time consumption in farming processes. Expected outcomes include the ability to perform multiple operations with ease, affordability for all farmers, and reduced maintenance costs. The conclusion emphasizes the potential impact of the machine in meeting the needs of small-scale farmers and overcoming traditional challenges, such as back pain from conventional spraying methods.

Bharath C H, Ruchitha R, Sneha K S, Sudeep G, Vashitha N Gowda. [2022], "Multipurpose Fabrication Machine Using Solar Power" in their design of solar powered vehicle, sun is the main source of energy for the vehicle. Energy from sun is captured by the solar panels and then this energy is converted to electrical energy. The electrical energy thus formed is being fed to the batteries that get charged and is used to run high torques DC series motor. The shaft of the motor is connected to the rear wheel of the vehicle by using chain sprocket.

B. Vinoth, M. Vinothpandiyar, R. Sethumadhavan, C. Pavithran [2021], They carried out a project to develop multipurpose agricultural vehicle, for performing major agricultural operations like ploughing, seeding, harvesting. The modification includes fabricating a vehicle which is small, compact in size. The project is about a machine design which makes cultivation much simpler. The design of the chassis of the vehicle is made in such a way that it is suitable for the operations. The design for automatic seed sowing equipment is made. The plough is designed and modified the currently available plough tool in such a way that it with stand the load. The harvester (cutter) is designed and working by scotch yoke mechanism.

Dilip Radkar, Goraksh Choughule, Abhijeet Desai, Prathamesh Gawand, Pradip Bade, Yogesh Chaudhari[2021],"Multipurpose Agriculture Machine "In this research paper author is mentioned about the features of plowing, planting, spraying, harvesting and transportation capabilities. The study also helped to overcomes the problem associated with conventional spray such as back pain due to weight carried on back on person.

Anveer, Manjunath Tolagatti, Manjunath Kharvi, Suhan Nayak, Manjunath L H [2020], The basic objective of sowing operation is to put the seed and fertilizer in rows at desired depth and seed to seed spacing. a wide role in agriculture field have discussed the seed sowing processes and tried to solve the problems, In seed sowing machine system they are used battery powered wheels and DC motor inbuilt in these wheels. When the seeds are empty it detects the level of storage seed and indicates the alarm. A rotavator is installed for soil preparation process to cut through larger soil lumps easily. A 22ltrs sprayer pump is installed for pesticide spraying operation. In this method system provides all the facility which can work efficiently.

Pratikkumar V. Patel Mukesh Ahuja [2020],"RESEARCH AND DESIGN OF MULTIPURPOSE AGRICULTURE EQUIPMENT", In this research paper, we found that how conventional machines can be designed into modern agricultural machine. The study also helped in the design of the fertilizer distributor that works with the help of seed hopper.

Jacek Caban, Jan Vrabec, Branislav Sarkan, Janusz Zarajczyk, Andrzej Marczuk[2018], has discussed the market of electric field tractors. There are individual models in offers dedicated to the agriculture made by foreign producers. However, these offers are presented mainly at agricultural fairs. The article presents the research on the needs of farms for electric tractors and presents the possibilities of developing electro mobility in this sector of the economy. Questionnaire was presented, data were collected from those working in the agricultural sector. The data will be used to gauge attitudes and opinions towards all tentative power systems implemented in agriculture.

Trupti A. Shinde, Jayashree.S. Awati [2017], In this research paper author has mentioned about the Design and Development of Automatic Seed Sowing Machine explores advancements in automatic seed sowing technology for agriculture. It shows the seed buckets are collected the seeds from the chamber and its sow required depth with the help of plough, user-friendly machines to facilitate precise seed placement and reduce manual labor. Key innovations include utilizing DC motors and battery to power up the wheels, ultrasonic sensors are used to detect the obstacles, low level indicator detects storage seeds and indicates the buzzer. We have taken those points in consideration while designing a Sowing operation to reduce the wastage of seeds and work efficiently.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Block Diagram of the Vehicle.

Fig 3.1.1: - Block Diagram of Agri-Vehicle

Designed by Using CATIA_V5 Software.

Fig 3.2.1: - Front & Back side view of the model

Fig 3.2.2: - Isometric view of the model

These are my 3D models designed by using CATIA_V5, are extensively used to development process of Agri vehicle, due to numerous advantages including accuracy, flexibility, and to ease to modify.

- Created a 3D digital model of the vehicle, incorporating its various components, such as chassis, motor, battery, solar panel, transmission, wheels, cultivators, cutter, fertilizer and Seed Sower.
- The individual components are assembled together to form the complete vehicle assembly has we shown in above figures ensuring that proper fittings and alignment.

Parts and its Operations.

a) Cultivator

Fig 3.3.1: - Cultivator

1-inch square Mild steel material is used for cultivator frame due to its strength, durability and also relatively low cost.

- By the help of hydraulic press, Bending the steel plates to create angles and curves for structural elements such as the main frame, cross section of the member, and mounting brackets.
- Components in position using clamps or fixtures to maintain alignment during welding.
- Applying surface treatments such as paint to protect the steel against corrosion.

b) Cutter

Fig 3.3.2: - Cutter

DC Motor is used to perform the operation due to its high torque, speed control, efficiency, and relatively low cost.

- High carbon steel blades offer excellences durability, strength and reliability, suitable for cutting thick or tough grass.
- By carefully fastening each screw, the DC motor is securely affixed to the frame, ready to power the blade attachments with precision and efficiency.

c) Hooper

Fig 3.3.3: - Hooper

- Hopper is mounted on chassis back to the engine, for stored seeds.
- Shank is the shaft of hopper for bowing seeds.

d) Sprayer

Fig 3.3.4: - Sprayer

- Sprayer is mounted on the end of chassis.

e) Fertilizer Tank

Fig 3.3.5: - Fertilizer Tank

- It is mounted on the back of the chassis between the battery and the motor
- For spraying operation pipe is connected to motor from the tank.

1) THEORETICAL CALCULATIONS

4.1 Calculation for Torque and Shaft: -

Weight of the Vehicle (m)= 80kg

Load(F)=m*g

$$F = 80 * 9.81$$

$$F = 784.8 \text{ N}$$

Diameter of sprocket(D)=80mm

Radius of sprocket(r)=40mm

Torque required to drive the wheel,

$$T = F * r$$

$$T = 784.8 * 0.040$$

$$T = 31.39 \text{ N-m}$$

The rated power (P)

Battery used,

$$12\text{V}, 7.5\text{Ah} + 6\text{V}, 4.5\text{Ah} = 18\text{V} * 12\text{Ah} = 216\text{watt}$$

$$P=216\text{watt}$$

We know that,

$$P = (2 * \pi * N * T) / 60$$

$$216 = (2 * \pi * N * 31.39) / 60$$

$$N = 65.71\text{rpm}$$

Speed of the vehicle,

$$V = \pi * D * N / 60$$

Were,

$$D = \text{diameter of the wheel} = 0.46\text{m}$$

1m/s = is equal to 3.6Km/hr

$$V = \pi * 0.46 * 65.71 / 60$$

$$V = 1.58 \text{ m/s}$$

$$V = 1.58 * 3.6$$

$$V = 5.6 \text{ Km/hr}$$

Speed of the Vehicle = 5 to 6 Km/hr

Torque, T = 31.39 N-m = 31390 N-mm

Now T is the maximum torque among all shaft, checking the shaft for failure

$$T = (\pi/16) * 135 * d^3$$

$$31390 = (3.14/16) * 135 * d^3$$

$$D = 10.57 = 11 \text{ mm}$$

But in this project, the diameter of the shaft is 26mm. So, the design is safe.

4.2 Calculation of the Axle Shaft: -

Consider the weight of 784.4 N is acting on the shaft,

Induced stress, $\sigma = M/Z$

Moment, $M = (WL)/4$

Where,

W = load

L = Length

$$M = (784.4 * 375)/4$$

$$M = 73575 \text{ N/mm}$$

Section modulus,

$$Z = (\pi/16) * d^3$$

$$Z = (\pi/16) * 26^3$$

$$Z = 3451.03 \text{ mm}^3$$

$$\sigma = M/Z$$

$$\sigma = (73575/3451.03)$$

$$\sigma = 21.31 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

Therefore, Induced stress < Allowed stress

$$21.31 \text{ N/mm}^2 < 270 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

(Hence the design is safe)

4.3 Calculations for Ploughing tool: -

Depth of cut = 0.05m

Speed of the tool as 5.5 km/hr

$$5.5 \text{ km/hr} * 1000 \text{ m/km} = 5500 \text{ m/hr}$$

$$5500 \text{ m/hr} / 60 \text{ min/hr} = 91.66 \text{ m/min}$$

No. of tool = 2

Feed rate can be calculated as,

$$= (\text{Speed of tool} * \text{depth of cut} * \text{Number of tool})$$

$$= 91.66 \text{ m/min} * 0.05 \text{ m} * 2$$

$$= 9.16 \text{ m}^2/\text{min}$$

Therefore, Considering Speed of tool, Depth of cut, Number of tool Optimal speed rate is 9.16 m²/min

4.4 Calculations for Seeding: -

Speed = 76 rpm

Row spacing = 25 cm

Seed sowing time = 2 seed/ sec Opening no = 2

$$\text{Seed dropping per minute} = 2 * 76 = 152 \text{ seeds}$$

Hence, if the speed of the wheel is 91 m/min, then for 91 meter 152 seeds will be dropped.

4.5 Calculations for Water sprinkler: -

Velocity of water,

Where,

V = Velocity of water

g = Gravity 9.81 m/s²
 h = Height from which the water is falling
 $v = \sqrt{2gh} = \sqrt{2 \times 9.81 \times 0.50} = 3.13 \text{ m/s}$
 Flow rate of the water,

SL. No	Description	Result
1	Feed rate of plough	9.16 m ² /min
2	Seed dropping rate at 91 m/min	152 Seeds
3	Time required to spray 4 liters	1 min
4	To charge the Battery by using solar panel	5Hrs 38min

$Q = \frac{\pi}{4} * v * d^2$
 $= 6.1457 * 10^{-5} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$
 Time for 4 Liter water tank,
 4 Liters = 0.004 m³/s
 $6.1457 * 10^{-5} \text{ m}^3 \dots \dots \dots > 1 \text{ sec}$
 $0.004 \text{ m}^3 \dots \dots \dots > ?$
 $t = 0.004 * 1 / 6.1457 * 10^{-5}$
 $t = 65.08 \text{ sec} / 60$
 $t = 1.08 \text{ min}$
 $t = 1 \text{ min}$

Hence, if the flow rate of water is 6.1457*10⁻⁵ m³/s approximately 4 Liters of water will be sprayed onto the land in 1 minute.

4.6 Calculation for Solar Panel: -

Using 12V, 20watts Solar panel to charge the 12V, 7.5Ah battery.

a) Solar panel output
 Considering 80% efficiency
 20watts * 0.80 = 16watts

b) Charging rate

$P = V I$

Were,

V = Voltage in volts

P = Power in watt

I = Current in amps

$P = V * I$

$16 = 12 * I$

$I = 1.33 \text{ A}$

c) Charging time

Time = Battery capacity / Charging current

$= 7.5 / 1.33$

Charging time = 5.63 hrs

Therefore, Charging the 12V, 7.5Ah Battery will take approximately 5 hours 38 minutes to reach full capacity.

CONCLUSION

This project entitled “DEVELOPMENT OF MULTIPURPOSE AGRI VEHICLE TO REDUCE THE FARMERS EFFORT”, is successfully completed and result obtained is satisfactory. Based on overall performance of the machine we can definitely say that the project will satisfy the need of small-scale farmers, if we manufacture in a large scale rapidly the cost gets reduces and we hope this will satisfy the rural side small scale Indian farmers. Partially the vehicle can be used for Ploughing, Sowing, Weed removing and also used for fertilizing. By the use of battery, the vehicle will help to reduce the air pollution by a large extent. Our team has successfully combined many ideas for various fields in mechanical engineering to reduce the draw backs in the agriculture fields. It will be more economical and efficient than heavy machines for small to medium scale farmers. Compare to the conventional method, it is much cost effective and reliable.

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